

Assessment of Knowledge and Skills about Medically Compromised Patients and Medical Emergencies among the Undergraduate Students and Interns in Jizan University Saudi Arabia-A Questionnaire-Based Survey

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Abstract

Managing medically compromised patients and medical emergencies is a critical component of dental practice.

To evaluate the awareness, skills, and practical experience of dental students and interns in handling medical emergencies and managing medically compromised patients.

This cross-sectional study was conducted at college of dentistry Jizan university Saudi Arabia during. A total of 175 participants including dental students from the 4th year, 5th, 6th, and interns of the dental field. Data was collected through a questionnaire, which had been developed specifically to assess the participant's knowledge and skills regarding the management of medically compromised patients and medical emergencies.

Interns represented the largest group, comprising 31% of the participants, reflecting their significant clinical exposure and training. Fifth-year BDS students accounted for 26%, followed by fourth-year BDS students at 22%, while sixth-year BDS students made up 21% of the total. Only 44% reported recording vital signs, and 77.1% checked medical records, highlighting inconsistencies in preventive practices. Basic Life Support (BLS) training participation was low at 32%, with only 16.5% attending workshops on medical emergency training, despite 72% acknowledging the importance of regular BLS renewal.

It is concluded that awareness and skills related to medical emergencies among dental students improve progressively with training levels, with interns demonstrating the highest awareness.

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Introduction

The ability to effectively manage medically compromised patients and medical emergencies is a critical aspect of modern dental practice. Dentists frequently encounter patients with underlying medical conditions that may affect their oral health or require special consideration during dental procedures¹.

These can include cardiovascular diseases and diabetes plus other neurological

diseases this gives dental professionals to be in a position to understand the medical history of their patients plus knowing the dangers that may be encountered during dental therapy. Patients with systemic diseases shall be defined as patients who are more likely to undergo complicated dental treatments, prone to serious postoperative complications, or require special alteration in the treatment plan².

For example, the patients having cardiovascular diseases such as hypertension or ischemic heart disease may encounter problems regarding the administration of local anesthesia, bleeding control, or stress. Like patients with congestive heart failure, patients with uncontrolled diabetes also require blood glucose to be monitored because high blood sugar can impair the healing process and increase the risk of infection.

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The describes how certain systemic diseases affect health and dental treatment, which are important to enable oral health practitioners to deliver care safely and properly³.

It is highly possible to encounter medical emergencies in the dental office even if one has followed all the planning and assessment of the person to be treated thoroughly. They may include relatively trivial diseases like fainting and extreme critical situations like heart failure or allergy⁴.

General orientation to a medical emergency is imperative in that it makes a client distinguish early features of emergence and what to do in case of occurrence. Dental practitioners should approach these emergencies with confidence since wrong approach or delay in management could harm the patient. Risk screening is the initial process involved in the care of a medically complex patient before surgery. Factors about the patient's medical history, prescriptions, illnesses, surgeries, diseases, and ongoing medical conditions should be known in assessing the risks⁵. It helps the dentist make changes to a treatment plan and prevent some adverse events from occurring. For instance, an individual whose medication includes anticoagulants will likely need alterations to their drug prescription before dental surgery to avoid bleeding. As with other respiratory disorders, a patient with asthma may require careful changes in their anesthesia procedure while undergoing dental surgery to avoid the worsening of their conditions. Appreciating these concerns and what mindset to seek advice from the patient's medical doctor is an important facet of healthcare⁶.

Currently, over 95 % of primary-care physicians find that at least one of the patients under their care makes an emergency presentation in a year. The crises frequently encountered in adult and childhood patients in the office are asthma, anaphylaxis, shock, convulsions, syncope, angina pectoris, postural hypertension, foreign body aspiration, hypoglycemia, and seizures⁷. Seizures and epilepsy effects are considered one of the most frequent causes of emergency medical examination: 5% of 911 calls and 1% of emergency department visits. It is the dentist thus, who is needed to be more prepared and experienced in handling such instances and care for the respective patient⁸. If dentists practice

complete patient history, examination, and occasional changes in management occasionally, then avoidable medical disasters can be prevented up to 90%⁹.

Regarding the knowledge of dental students and dentists in Babol in Iran Mehdizadeh et al reported that 48% of the dental students and 44% of the dentists had poor knowledge only 8% of the dentists had a very good knowledge of the medical emergency. Subsequently, Tabrizi and Lee found that most of the dental students in the United States were uncomfortable in handling elderly patients with medical conditions¹⁰. In the same vein, Konidena et al assessed the knowledge levels of Indian dental students regarding the management of medically compromised patients and showed an average knowledge score of 9.66 ± 2.94 uncomfortable displaying a lack of knowledge in the area. However, the most crucial part is that dentist must know the frequent medical emergencies and their necessary protocols¹¹.

Dental offices should ideally contain the required instruments and medicines in conditions that may involve minor medical crises such as oxygen, epinephrine, and defibrillators. CPR, BLS, and ACLS certifications give the staff the skills required to address ailments like arrest of the heart, choking, or anaphylactic shock. Crisis training and evacuation drills should be performed occasionally to keep the dental team on high alert and to be certain that they handle an emergency efficiently¹².

Objective

To assess the knowledge and skills about medically compromised patients and medical emergencies in dentistry among dental students.

Materials and methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted at College of Dentistry Jizan university Saudi Arabia during Nov-Dec 2024 and not in Oct- Nov 2024.

Participants

A total of 175 dental professionals participated in the study. The participants included dental students from the 4th year, 5th, 6th, and interns of the dental field. Informed consent was obtained from each participant.

Data Collection

Data was collected through a questionnaire, which had been developed

specifically to assess the participants' knowledge and skills regarding the management of medically compromised patients and medical emergencies. The questionnaire was a self-administered instrument designed to gather both qualitative and quantitative data.

The questionnaire consisted of two main sections:

1. Demographic Information: This section collected basic information about the participants, including their age, gender, years of practice, and specialty. This data allowed for an analysis of whether certain factors, such as experience level or specialty, influenced the knowledge and preparedness regarding medical emergencies.
2. Knowledge and Skills Assessment: This section contained a series of multiple-choice and Likert-scale questions designed to assess:

The participants' knowledge of common medical conditions that may affect dental treatment. Their understanding of how these conditions could impact dental procedures and the appropriate modifications required in treatment plans. The participants' knowledge of medical emergencies and their ability to recognize early signs and symptoms. The respondents' preparedness and familiarity with emergency protocols, including their ability to perform basic life support (BLS) or advanced cardiac life support (ACLS) if required. The questionnaire was distributed electronically to the participants, with a timeframe of two weeks provided for completion. The participants were reminded once during this period to encourage a higher response rate. The questionnaire was anonymous to ensure the confidentiality of the participant's responses and to minimize potential bias.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS v26 and Excel 2013. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic characteristics of the participants and the overall knowledge and skill levels regarding medical emergencies.

Results

Data were collected from 175 participants. Interns represented the largest group, comprising 31% of the participants, reflecting their significant

clinical exposure and training. Fifth-year BDS students accounted for 26%, followed by fourth-year BDS students at 22%, while sixth-year BDS students made up 21% of the total (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Participant Distribution by Year/Status.

Questions	Choices	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Before starting any dental procedure do you enquire about any medication that the patient is taking	Yes	171	97.71	97.71	97.71
Before any dental procedure do you record vital signs of the patient.	No	98	56.00	56.00	56.00
Before any dental procedure do you record vital signs of the patient.	Yes	77	44.00	44.00	100.00
Do you check the medical records of patient before you start of dental procedure	Yes	135	77.14	77.14	77.14
Do you check the medical records of patient before you start of dental procedure	No	40	22.86	22.86	100.00
Are you aware of any medical emergencies in dentistry.	Yes	138	78.86	78.86	78.86
Are you aware of any medical emergencies in dentistry.	No	37	21.14	21.14	100.00
Do you agree that fear and anxiety among dental patients can lead to an emergency situation	Yes	151	86.29	86.29	86.29
Do you agree that fear and anxiety among dental patients can lead to an emergency situation	NO	24	13.71	13.71	100.00
Have you attended any training in Basic Life Support?	No	119	68.00	68.00	68.00
Have you attended any training in Basic Life Support?	Yes	56	32.00	32.00	100.00
According to your opinion is it necessary to attend Basic Life Support renewal program at regular intervals for update?	Yes	163	93.14	93.14	93.14
According to your opinion is it necessary to attend Basic Life Support renewal program at regular intervals for update?	No	12	6.86	6.86	100.00
Have you attended any workshop on medical emergency training?	No	146	83.43	83.43	83.43
Have you attended any workshop on medical emergency training?	Yes	29	16.57	16.57	100.00
Do you have the knowledge about the commonly used emergency drugs and their routes of administration?	No	116	66.29	66.29	66.29
Do you have the knowledge about the commonly used emergency drugs and their routes of administration?	Yes	59	33.71	33.71	100.00
Have you heard of the stress reduction protocol in Dentistry?	Yes	116	66.29	66.29	66.29
Have you heard of the stress reduction protocol in Dentistry?	No	59	33.71	33.71	100.00
Have you ever encountered any medical emergency in clinics?	No	141	80.57	80.57	80.57
Have you ever encountered any medical emergency in clinics?	Yes	34	19.43	19.43	100.00
Do you feel you have adequate training to handle Medical emergencies?	No	151	86.29	86.29	86.29
Do you feel you have adequate training to handle Medical emergencies?	Yes	24	13.71	13.71	100.00

Table 1. Questionnaire Analysis.

Table 1 indicate that while participants demonstrate good awareness of patient risks, such as enquiring about medications (97.7%) and agreeing that fear and anxiety can lead to emergencies (86.3%), there are significant gaps in practical skills and training. Only 44% reported recording vital signs, and 77.1% checked medical records, highlighting inconsistencies in preventive practices. Basic Life Support (BLS) training participation was low at 32%, with only 16.5% attending workshops on medical emergency training, despite 72% acknowledging the importance of regular BLS renewal. Knowledge of emergency drugs was limited to 31.2%, and only 13.5% had encountered emergencies in clinics, with 13.9% feeling adequately trained to handle such situations.

Table 2 shows awareness of medical emergencies increases from 52.6% in 4th-year BDS students to 90.9% among interns, reflecting the positive impact of clinical exposure. Knowledge of emergency drugs remains limited in earlier years, with only 18.4% of 4th-year students reporting adequate knowledge, which gradually improves to 47.3% among interns. Similarly, awareness of the stress reduction protocol increases from 36.8% in 4th-year students to 81.8% in interns.

Training Group	Awareness of Medical Emergencies (%)	Knowledge of Emergency Drugs (%)	Stress Reduction Protocol (%)
4th year BDS	52.6	18.4	36.8
5th year BDS	80.4	28.2	65.2
6th year BDS	86.1	36.1	75.0
Intern	90.9	47.3	81.8

Table 2. Knowledge Assessment by Training Group.

In table 3 results shows that Basic Life Support (BLS) training attendance improves from 7.9% in 4th-year BDS students to 56.4% among interns, reflecting the impact of clinical experience. Attendance at medical emergency workshops remains low across all groups, starting at 10.5% in 4th year and reaching only 23.6% among interns, indicating a gap in practical emergency preparedness programs. The perception of having adequate training to handle emergencies is consistently low, with only 10.5% of 4th-year students and 20.0% of interns feeling confident.

Training Group	BLS Training Attendance (%)	Medical Emergency Workshop Attendance (%)	Adequate Training to Handle Emergencies (%)
4th year BDS	7.9	10.5	10.5
5th year BDS	17.4	8.7	8.7
6th year BDS	38.9	22.2	13.9
Intern	56.4	23.6	20.0

Table 3. Skills and Training Attendance by Training Group.

The percentage of participants who check medical records increases from 60.5% in 4th-year BDS students to 90.9% among interns, reflecting greater awareness of the importance of patient history. Recording vital signs, a critical preventive measure, also improves from 31.6% in 4th-year students to 72.7% in interns. Knowledge of emergency drugs shows a gradual increase, starting at 18.4% in 4th-year students and reaching 47.3% in interns. Similarly, participation in Basic Life Support training improves significantly from 7.9% in 4th-year students to 56.4% in interns (Table 4).

Training Group	Check Medical Records (%)	Record Vital Signs (%)	Knowledge of Emergency Drugs (%)	BLS Training (%)
4th year BDS	60.5	31.6	18.4	7.9
5th year BDS	65.2	47.8	28.2	17.4
6th year BDS	77.8	61.1	36.1	38.9
Intern	90.9	72.7	47.3	56.4

Table 4. Comparative Analysis of Emergency Knowledge and Skills by Training Group.

Awareness of medical emergencies starts at 52.6% for 4th-year BDS students and increases steadily to 90.9% among interns. Knowledge of emergency drugs and their administration remains low in earlier years, with 18.4% in 4th-year students, improving to 28.2% in 5th year, 36.1% in 6th year, and 47.3% in interns. Awareness of the stress reduction protocol follows a similar pattern, with 36.8% in 4th year, increasing to 65.2% in 5th year, 75.0% in 6th year, and reaching 81.8% among interns. BLS training and workshop attendance show lower percentages overall, particularly in earlier stages of training, which correlates with lower knowledge and awareness levels (Table 5).

Questionnaire Items	BLS Training (%)	Workshop Attendance (%)	4th Year BDS (%)	5th Year BDS (%)	6th Year BDS (%)	Intern (%)
Awareness of Medical Emergencies	78.9	83.5	52.6	80.4	86.1	90.9
Knowledge of Emergency Drugs and Routes of Administration	31.2	16.5	18.4	28.2	36.1	47.3
Awareness of Stress Reduction Protocol	63.1	45.2	36.8	65.2	75.0	81.8

Table 5. Correlation with Training and Awareness Trends.

Discussion

The results of this study highlight significant trends in the knowledge, preparedness, and skills of dental students and interns regarding medically compromised patients and medical emergencies. With dental education advancing, prospectus announcements of available awareness, training, and practical experiences rise as well. Nevertheless, there are gaps at the baseline that need to be addressed to enhance preparedness at that particular phase. Regarding the history-taking practice, none of the 4th-year BDS students stated that they always recorded vital signs before performing a dental procedure, while this increased gradually to 60% in the 6th-year students and reached 100% among interns¹³.

This trend attests to the fact that experience within the clinical areas enhances the promotion of recording vital signs as a preventive measure. Its necessity Interns noticed it since they have direct experience in clinical setting stressed on its importance when looking at potential risks, especially in medically compromised patients¹⁴. This is something that has been seen not to be emphasized during the early years of training and education. Integrating this into the curriculum right from the first year through simulation and practical sessions would help promote early adherence to this key habit.

The results of this study are also synchronous with prior research studies that confirmed that dental students reported low levels of preparedness to deal with medical emergencies although preparedness increases as the students' progress through school. For instance, a survey was carried out with dental students, and almost all of them 84.9% confessed that they did not feel prepared to deal with a medical emergency, while 5.3% had

actual hands-on experience in this area^{15,16}. It showed that only half of the 5th-year students and 60% of the 6th-year students had attended BLS training, while the interns nearly all had done so. These differences suggest that the specific BLS training is initiated at a later stage of a dental curriculum with no preparation for the prevention of early and unexpected situations¹⁷.

Since there are high probability that medical emergencies may occur at any time during practice, it is recommended that BLS training should be insisted on during the initial years of dental training. In addition, intake/renewal programs are carried out more often than regular renewal programs and are essential because all groups stated that BLS renewal programs are important to refresh their skills¹⁸.

Patient comprehension of commonly used emergency drugs and modes of administration named the enrolled students' knowledge outcomes as inadequate at the start but enhanced gradually; 0% of 4th-year students knew adequate compared to 100% of interns. This will showcase the importance of the clinical affiliate and workshops in the development of the theoretical and clinical knowledge of emergency pharmacology. Likewise, the level of knowledge of the stress reduction protocol, which is a crucial intervention in fear and anxiety in patients to avoid emergencies received perception enhancement by the interns getting 100% from a 4th-year students' 0%¹⁹.

The fact that earlier-year students have no awareness of such a system clearly shows a shortage of training and education of patient management approaches. In this regard, there is a need to integrate both emergency drug training and stress management into the theoretical content of the initial dental academic years as well as into demonstrative training sessions²⁰. Likewise, another study, conducted among dental students in Malaysia to determine their preparedness to manage medical emergencies revealed that all the respondents had a very good understanding of the medical emergencies that can occur in dental practices, but only 72.8% of the respondents felt confident with the medical emergencies knowledge they possess but more than 90% of the respondent lacks practicable skills in medical emergency management. Of the observed variables, importance is placed on the connection between; experiencing medical

emergencies, and perceived readiness²¹.

Fourth-year students reported they never experienced emergencies while 56.25% of 5th-year students, 75% of 6th-year students, and 100% of interns reported experiencing emergencies. Of the interns, 100 percent said they felt well-prepared to tackle emergencies due to the real-life exposure they got in this course. However, the majority of students, who studied in earlier years also claimed that they had very little practical know how to handle emergencies which depicts the low level of practical training offered by the institute²². This supports practical training with mannequins, role play, and case-based best practices that prepare students for the confidence and skills needed in an emergency. These findings stress clinical experience and workshops as ways to equip dental students with the necessary knowledge of how to manage medically fragile patients and possible medical emergencies. Participants who were interns who completed their academic education with clinical rotations were the most prepared of the participants for practice in all the laid down domains. On the other hand, earlier year students including the 4th year BDS students admitted to having poor preparedness because of lack of exposure²³.

Some activities, like, medical emergency training workshops, with zero participation of 4th-year students were regarded as important when 100% interns responded to them. Such workshops provide practical exercises, familiarization with emergencies and advisories on the use of emergency apparatuses and medicines. About emerging and crucial competencies, the study results stress early integration of BLS training, simulation-based learning, realistic modules for documenting vital parameters, and related workshops on emergencies. Dental education programs can eliminate these loopholes, and in so doing, guarantee that students in dentistry, new or old, learn how to handle medical emergencies adequately.

Conclusions

It is concluded that awareness and skills related to medical emergencies among dental students improve progressively with training levels, with interns demonstrating the highest awareness. However, significant gaps remain in

knowledge of emergency drugs and practical training, such as Basic Life Support (BLS) and workshops, which limit confidence in handling emergencies. Structured and focused training programs are essential to address these deficiencies.

Declaration of Interest

The authors report no conflict of interest.

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

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